

IMPROVING SPEAKING SKILLS OF A2 LEVEL STUDENTS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS.

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***Abstract:** This article deals with the problems and solutions of improving speaking skills in A2 level students, and some important methods in teaching the speaking skill while using the target language.*

***Key words:** classroom, speakers, abilities, activities, correcting.*

INTRODUCTION

As Scott Thornbury suggests, that the teaching of speaking depends on there being a classroom culture of speaking, and that classrooms need to become 'talking classrooms'. In other words, students will be much more confident speakers (and their speaking abilities will improve) if this kind of speaking activation is a regular feature of lessons. Famous people: students think of five famous people. They have to decide on the perfect gift for each person. We can also get groups of students to decide on which five famous people (living or dead) they would most like to invite for dinner, what they would talk about and what food they would give them. It will probably be necessary for teachers to correct mistakes made during speaking activities in a different way from those made during a study exercise. It will probably be necessary for teachers to correct mistakes made during speaking activities in a different way from those made during a study exercise.

METHODS

But if the same teacher did this while students were involved in a passionate discussion about whether smoking should be banned on tourist beaches, for example, the effect might well be to destroy the conversational flow. If, just at the moment one of the students is making an important point, the teacher says

‘Hey wait, you said “is” but it should be “are”, beaches are ... repeat’, the point will quickly be lost. Constant interruption from the teacher will destroy the purpose of the speaking activity. Here we give some speaking activities. **Describing people:** students will be divided into three small groups, and given some pictures of famous people for describing. And also there will be given some adjectives to use in the description. **Meeting and greeting:** students role-play a formal/business social occasion where they meet a number of people and introduce themselves. [1] Both of them are the best games to improve students’ speaking skills, which leads the students to learn to behave themselves in large auditoriums as well as, in conferences, while presenting some kind of topics.

H. G. Widowson distinguished two aspects of performance: 1) usage one aspect which makes evident the context rules, 2) use is another aspect which makes evident the context of which the language user demonstrate his/her ability to use the knowledge of linguistic rules for effective communication. [2] Both these aspects of performance are required as “linguistic performance involves the simultaneous manifestation of the language system as usage and realization as use. [3]

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Many teachers watch and listen while speaking activities are taking place. They note down things that seemed to go well and times when students couldn’t make themselves understood or made important mistakes. When the activity has finished, they then ask the students how they thought it went before giving their own feedback. They may say that they liked the way Student A said this, and the way Student B was able to disagree with her. They will then say that they did hear one or two mistakes, and they can discuss them with the class, write them on the board or give them individually to the students concerned. In each case, they will ask the students to see if they can identify the problem and correct it. As with any kind of correction, it is important not to single students out for particular criticism. Many teachers deal with the mistakes they heard without saying

who was responsible for them. Of course, there are no hard and fast rules about correcting. Some teachers who have a good relationship with their students can intervene appropriately during a speaking activity if they do it in a quiet non-obtrusive way. This kind of gentle correction might take the form of reformulation where the teacher repeats what the student has said, but correctly this time, and does not ask for student repetition of the corrected form. Some students do prefer to be told at exactly the moment they make a mistake; but we always have to be careful to make sure that our actions do not compromise the activity in question.

Some teachers get very involved with their students during a speaking activity and want to participate in the activity themselves! They may argue forcefully in a discussion or get fascinated by a role-play and start ‘playing’ themselves. There’s nothing wrong with teachers getting involved, of course, provided they don’t start to dominate. Although it is probably better to stand back so that you can watch and listen to what’s going on, students can also appreciate teacher participation at the appropriate level - in other words, not too much! Sometimes, however, teachers will have to intervene in some way if the activity is not going smoothly. If someone in a role-play can’t think of what to say, or if a discussion begins to dry up, the teacher will have to decide if the activity should be stopped - because the topic has run out of steam - or if careful prompting can get it going again. That’s where the teacher may make a point in a discussion or quickly take on a role to push a role-play forward. Prompting is often necessary but, as with correction, teachers should do it sympathetically and sensitively.[1]

CONCLUSION

Perhaps the best way of correcting speaking activities appropriately is to talk to students about it. You can ask them how and when they would prefer to be corrected; you can explain how you intend to correct during these stages, and show them how different activities may mean different correction behavior on your part. During the practical period at the secondary school I analyzed that the students of

A2 level are very much interested in speaking part of the lesson, which is usually called the production stage of the lesson, they are keen on participating in group discussions, and also in taking part in individual activities, which provide them to use the target language freely, rather than in controlled practice activities.

According to Jeremy Harmer, how speaking activities provide opportunities for rehearsal, give both teacher and students feedback and motivate students because of their engaging qualities. Above all, they help students to be able to produce language automatically - a crucial stage on the way to autonomy.

[1] We are agreeing that giving feedback to students at the end of the lesson especially a positive feedback motivates the students.

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